

PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS BY TiO₂ POWDER

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1. Introduction

Phenolic compounds are found in wastewater from the refinery industries. They have aromatic ring structures causing difficult removal and become toxic in the environment. [1-3] Photocatalysts such as TiO₂ and ZnO under UV-light irradiation can degrade phenolic compounds. TiO₂ is an excellent photocatalyst because it is non toxic, insoluble in water and cheap. TiO₂ (anatase) has an energy band gap of 3.2 eV which can be activated by UV-light with wavelengths under 388 nm that resulting in degradation of organic compound into harmless CO₂ and H₂O. [5-7]

The objective of this work is to study the degradation kinetics and degradation products resulted from the photodegradation of phenolic compounds under UV irradiation using TiO₂ catalyst.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

Titanium dioxide (TiO₂-P25) as photocatalyst was supplied from Degussa Chemicals. Phenol (PH), acetophenone (ACP) and cumene hydroperoxide (CHP) as representative phenolic compounds in wastewater were purchased from Merck Chemical Co. and reverse Osmosis water (Siam, Thailand) was used to prepare all solutions.

2.2 Photocatalytic activity experiment

Phenol, acetophenone and cumene hydroperoxide solutions were prepared at 30 ppm concentration. and 0.05 g of TiO₂-P25 was mixed with 20 ml of each solution and then the pH was adjusted by HCl

and NaOH to about 7. The photocatalytic experiment of each phenolic compound was performed in a cabinet with UV lamps at intensity of 2 mW/cm². The solution was stirred in the dark for 1 hour and then irradiated by UV-light for 1, 2, 3 and 4 hours. The sample was centrifuge for 20 min in order to remove the photocatalyst powder before measuring the absorbance by a UV-Vis spectrophotometer.

2.3 Characterization

X-ray diffractometry (XRD, Bruker D8 Advance), UV-Vis spectrophotometry (Perkin Elmer, Lambda 35) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC, HEWLETT PACKARD SERIES 1100 with column condition: thermoscientific® Hypersil Gold, particle size 1.9 μm C18) were used to characterize the mineral phases of the photocatalyst, content and type of the degradation products, respectively.

3. Results

Fig 1-3 shows the UV-Vis spectra of the degradation of PH, ACP and CHP with and without photocatalysts. The results indicates that without TiO₂-P25 catalyst, there is hardly any change in absorbance observed. In presence of the catalyst, the absorbances in the short wavelength range (upto 240 nm) of the phenolic compounds clearly decrease with increasing irradiation time. The increase in the absorbance of CHP over that in the dark in the long wavelength range (>240nm) suggesting the evolution

of intermediates. It is found that the degradation of phenolic compounds follows pseudo-first order reaction and the order of degradation rates is $ACP > CHP > PH$ and all the results of the photocatalytic experiment are summarized in Table 1.

Fig.2. Absorbance of CHP (a) w/o P25 (b) P25 0.05g

Fig.1. Absorbance of PH (a) w/o P25 (b) P25 0.05g

Fig.3. Absorbance of ACP (a) w/o P25 (b) P25 0.05g

Table1. the content of products, efficiency of degradation and rate constant after UV irradiation for 4h.

Phenolic compounds	Condition	Concentration (ppm)					Efficiency of degradation (%)	rate* constant(k,1/h)
		Dark 1h	UV1h	UV2h	UV3h	UV4h		
Phenol	w/o P25	30.00	30.00	29.61	27.62	27.13	9.57	-
	+P25 (0.05g)	30.00	18.61	9.95	6.15	3.28	89.07	0.58
ACP	w/o P25	30.00	22.25	16.85	15.68	9.32	68.93	0.27
	+P25 (0.05g)	30.00	2.70	1.70	0.26	0.13	99.57	1.35
CHP	w/o P25	30.00	30.00	30.00	29.77	29.45	1.83	-
	+P25 (0.05g)	30.00	10.78	3.83	0.00	0.00	100.00	1.08

* The rate constants in Table 1 are calculated from the equation

$$kt = \ln \frac{C_0}{C_t}$$

k is the apparent rate constant (1/h)
 C_0 is the initial concentration (ppm).
 C_t is the concentration at t h UV irradiation (ppm).

Conclusion

PH and CHP are hardly degraded by photolysis but almost completely degraded by photocatalysis in 4 h. ACP can be degraded by both photolysis and photocatalysis, but the latter is much more effective. The identified intermediate product of PH and CHP during photocatalysis. The degradation rates, in receding order are ACP > CHP > PH.

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